

Language colonization or lingua franca? Demystifying the status quo of Persian

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Persian, the lingua franca of Iran, is spoken as a mother tongue by all monolingual or polyglot Iranian citizens who belong to a rich variety of pedigree-Iranian ethnic populations, including Gilak, Mazandarani, Baloch, Azerbaijani, Turkmen, Qashqai, Assyrian, Armenian, Lur, Talysh, Tat, and so on. There are random political dissidents who desperately desire to sell their myth that Persian has long been a ‘colonizing’ force, but the vast majority of Iranians earnestly argue that Persian has never been a ‘colonizing’ language; it has always been a lingua franca or a language of communication freely and consciously chosen by the inhabitants of the Iranian plateau who cherished it throughout history. This paper (a) draws on the existing literature on ‘language colonization’ and ‘language weaponization’ to afford a clear understanding of these topics and (b) aims at demystifying the status quo of Persian. It concludes that Persian has never been a colonizing force and argues that the ‘teaching *of* local languages’ is quite acceptable, but ‘teaching *in* local languages’ is the call by radical separatist groups who aim at the disintegration of a historically-unified nation.

Keywords: Linguaging; Language Activism; Language Colonization; Language Equity; Language Weaponization; Linguistic Diversity; Translinguaging

1. Introduction

Perhaps the earliest realization of the role of a language in the ‘structuring’ of a nation dates back to Samuel Johnson’s conception of a nation’s language as its ‘pedigree’ (Boswell, 1998[1785]), a term—borrowed from zoology—that shows the record of descent of a species that testifies to its being ‘pure-bred’—e.g., pedigree cats. A nation is a ‘biologically pedigree’ nation if the biological record of descent of its ethnic groups shows that they come from the same biological origin; similarly, it is a ‘socially pedigree’ nation if, à la Samuel Johnson, the record of descent of its national language shows that they, collectively, have historically spoken that language as their mother tongue.

Later on, Humboldt (1836, p. LXVI) expressed a similar view in his famous quotation, “*Die Sprache ist das bildende Organ des Gedanken*” (i.e., language is the formative organ of thought), to connect language and thought (cf. Allan,

2021) which was later turned into the famous Sapir-Whorf Hypothesis—i.e., ‘linguistic relativity’ (Salmani Nodoushan, 2021a). The Sapir-Whorf hypothesis considers world views to be mediated by linguistic structures (Allan, 2021; see also Boas, 1911; Sapir, 1929; Steintal, 1848; Whitney, 1875; Whorf, 1956). According to Sapir (1949[1933]), “Language is a great force of socialization, probably the greatest that exists” (p. 159).

These claims became precursors to an uncharted territory of sociolinguistic and anthropological inquiry, which has more recently come to be known as ‘language socialization’, a theory that proffers the idea that both ‘language’ and ‘socialization’ simultaneously lend to and borrow from each other in that (a) language spurs socialization and (b) socialization paves the way for language acquisition (cf. Schieffelin & Ochs, 1986a; 1986b; see also LeVine et al., 1994; Mead, 1928; Mead, 1934; Parsons, 1951; Whiting et al., 1975). Debates on the interface between language and socialization have more recently motivated new controversial topics, including language activism, language colonization, language equity, language weaponization, linguistic diversity, languaging, translanguaging, and so forth. A discussion of these topics is out of scope here, but the interested reader is invited to see Balosa (2024), Chaka (2006, 2023, 2024), Huang (2024), Kruger-Marais (2024), Mapuya (2024), Motaung (2024), Ndlangamandla (2024), Ndlangamandla et al. (2024), Nkhi and Shange (2024), and Xu and Fang (2024)—among others.

Persian, as the pedigree ‘lingua franca’ of communication in Iran, is spoken by Iranian citizens, who belong to a rich variety of pedigree-Iranian cultural populations encompassing Gilak, Mazandarani, Baloch, Azerbaijani, Turkmen, Qashqai, Assyrian, Armenian, Lur, Talysh, Tat, and so on. Nevertheless, there are random political dissidents who desperately desire to sell their myth that Persian has long been a colonizing force; the vast majority of Iranians earnestly argue that Persian has never been a colonizing language, though. The majority Iranian group argues that Persian has historically been a lingua franca or a language of communication freely and consciously chosen by the inhabitants of the Iranian plateau who have cherished it throughout history. This paper (a) draws on the existing literature on ‘language colonization’ and ‘language weaponization’ to afford a clear understanding of these topics and (b) aims at demystifying the status quo of Persian. I will follow a line of argumentation that shows why the myth propagated by random political dissidents is invalid.

2. Background

Central to the main discussion of the current paper is the understanding of two important topics: (a) linguistic colonialism, and (b) language weaponization. In this section, a brief overview of these topics is presented.

2.1. Linguistic colonialism

Linguistic colonialism is roughly defined as the ‘transfer’ of an invading hegemonic language to ‘colonized’ people in remote areas of the world whose native language has few commonalities with the colonizing language. Historically, linguistic colonization has come about through ‘soft’ or ‘hard’ mechanisms (e.g., military invasion, economic relations, trade, political dominance, etc.) in different parts of the globe (cf. Phillipson, 1992, 2013). It has been argued in the relevant literature that the culture of the colonial force also gets transferred to the colonized nation (Kamusella, 2020). Phillipson (1992) used the cover term ‘linguistic imperialism’ to refer to the idea of an alien language overtaking territories in which it did not belong. Examples include (1) English in parts of Asia, Africa, Oceania, and America, (2) Spanish in South America, and (3) French in Africa and the Middle East.

At the heart of Phillipson’s (1992) conception of linguistic imperialism lies the idea that the colonizing or invading power uses linguisticism—i.e., ‘militant’ or ‘systemic’ linguisticism—to impose linguistic or dialectal ‘discrimination’ (cf. Skutnabb-Kangas & Phillipson, 1995). Linguicism, one form of which is linguistic imperialism, refers to ‘structures’ as well as ‘ideologies’ that are brought to bear on the ‘legitimization’, ‘effectuation’, and ‘reproduction’ of inequality in (a) power and (b) access to resources—ideologies that do so through language-driven discrimination. Examples of linguistic inequality and/or discrimination include accent prejudice, dialect prejudice, English-only movement, language planning, linguistic stigmatization, native speakerism, and so forth. Just like ‘sexism’, ‘racism’, anti-Semitism, Islamism, etc., that inflict discrimination/segregation on groups of people based on sex, race, religion, etc., linguisticism—as its ardent critics honestly believe—inflicts language-based discrimination. Through linguisticism, language is turned into a tool that can effectuate and maintain unequal access to, and allocation of, social and/or political power and material, economic, developmental, educational, and other forms of resources (cf. Conama & Rose, 2018; also see Chaka, 2006, 2023). All in all, linguistic imperialism boils down into ideologically-laden and language-driven asymmetrical access to infrastructures, opportunities, and resources.

Linguistic colonization, a form of linguistic imperialism or the enactment of it, has historically taken place in different parts of the world mainly due to the arrival of traders, settlers, or exploiters upon new stretches of land. Whether colonization takes place through trade, settlement, invasion, exploitation, or otherwise, its impacts are not the same. African pidgin languages (e.g., Nigerian Pidgin or Cameroonian Pidgin) are a good case in point; they illustrate how ‘trade ties’ between indigenous peoples of African West Coast and European colonists have resulted in the emergence of pidgin languages—a situation that has also been observed in the Americas (Mufwene, 2001, 2015). The traders

did not impose their own European languages on the indigenous peoples of Africa. Rather, they and their African interlocutors resorted to a new *lingua franca* (i.e., a pidgin language) that did not pose any threats to indigenous languages of the African people. The separate and disparate European and indigenous African languages got 'hybridized' in that they produced new entities (i.e., pidgins) that (a) shared features with both European and indigenous African languages, and (b) were not purely compositional.

Historically, merchant colonizers were quite often followed by new settlers coming from Europe to settle on the new lands. New settlers introduced new ways of colonization, which were not as peaceful as the ways adopted by earlier trade colonizers. Settler colonizers brought new diseases and wars with them—mainly to places like Mexico, Uruguay, Brazil, Argentina, the Caribbean, and so forth (Hamel, 2008).¹ According to Hamel, they used 'segregation', 'isolation', and 'integration' as their preferred ways of interaction with target indigenous cultures. The wars and diseases that settler colonizers brought with them resulted in the loss of many native indigenous languages mainly in Central and South Americas—and maybe in other parts of the globe. Nevertheless, in some countries such as Mexico, Guatemala, and the Andean states, the settler colonizers and the indigenous people preferred 'integration' to 'segregation' or 'isolation'; the result has been a new hybrid that comprises a mixture of colonists' and indigenous peoples' languages and cultures. Adopting European social and political order in such countries has resulted in the acceptance of colonial languages (e.g., Spanish, Portuguese, etc.) for governance and industry (Hamel, 2008).

In other places, exploiter colonizers opted for strategies that had not been part of the agenda of merchant and settler colonizers. Exploiter colonizers firmly believed that the development of unified nation-states in their new settlements did indeed require the eradication of local indigenous societies, cultures, and traditions. In Canada and the USA, for instance, white colonizers ardently opted for the destruction of native tribal languages and cultures. The famous anecdote of the Comanche Chief who reportedly told Sheridan in 1869 that Indians are good people quotes Sheridan to have supposedly responded by saying, 'The only good Indians I ever saw were dead' (Mieder, 1993). Later on in the 20th century, aboriginal and native children were sent to boarding schools where they received the type of education that would make them ready to socialize into the new colonial society. As a result of the strategies practiced by exploiter colonizers in mainly exploitative colonies (like the United States, Canada, and Australia), only a few people speak indigenous languages these days. Needless to say, it may look somewhat odd that I have used the term 'exploiter colonizers' to refer to the white people who have 'settled' in places like United States, Canada, and Australia; some would say these are settler colonies (e.g., Mufwene, 2001) in that the white people have indeed 'settled' in

them rather than opting for the extraction of raw materials which they needed in Europe. Although this claim might apparently be true, the white people in the United States, Canada, Australia, and many other places have not only exploited their raw materials but also their whole lands. Hence, exploiter colonizers.

All in all, linguistic colonialism and imperialism fall under the cover term 'linguicism' that, according to Conama and Rose (2018), has several defining features, the most distinctive of which are listed here:

- linguicism favors the dominant language over other languages in much the same way as racism favors a race over others, or sexism favors one sex over another or one gender over others;
- linguicism is a structurally-manifested hegemonic ideology that allocates many more resources and infrastructures to the dominant language;
- linguicism encourages claims that assign more prestige to the dominant language;
- linguicism is a structural approach in that it envisages structural 'homology'—à la cultural studies (cf. Barker, 2004; Willis, 1978)—for language along with culture, education, media, and politics;
- linguicism is essentially exploitative in that it causes injustice and inequality between those who do and don't use the dominant language; and
- linguicism has a subtractive impact on other languages in that learning the dominant language takes place at the expense of the non-dominant (or recessive) languages.

These defining features of linguistic colonialism and imperialism tacitly imply that the dominant language has to be used as a weapon in the structuring of the society. This brings us to the second pillar on which the main argument of the current paper stands: language weaponization.

2.2. Language weaponization

Language weaponization—I prefer 'the weaponization of language', though—refers to the process in which any form of language (including words, utterances, discourse, etc.) is willfully wielded to inflict harm on individuals or groups of people through practices, ideologies, and/or policies that overtly or covertly pursue and normalize inequity and injustice (Bryan & Pentón Herrera, 2024b). Language weaponization can result in physical, emotional, social, and/or economic disadvantages for, or harms to, individuals or groups; it can minoritize and stigmatize their personality, social status, culture, or language. According to Pentón Herrera and Bryan (2022), "language weaponization can

and has resulted [*sic*] in negation, subjugation, mistreatment, slavery, segregation, physical and emotional harm, violence, and death” (p. 2). They further define language weaponization as the “use of language to benefit some and offend, marginalize, or dehumanize others based on skin color, race and ethnicity, gender(s), sexuality(ies), nationality(ies), languages spoken, religion, and/or (dis)abilities” (p. 2).

Pentón Herrera and Bryan (2022) claim that a person whose native language, gender, or race has been privileged has—by virtue of that privilege—access to political and social benefits and advantages that are not allocated or open to (a) Black, Indigenous, and People of Color (i.e., BIPOC), (b) nonnative English speakers, (c) women, and (d) LGBTQ+ individuals. This claim is based on the assumption that language has the capacity to empower or disempower; it can partially and asymmetrically affect the lives of individuals and communities as well as their cultures on social and political planes (Pentón Herrera & Bryan, 2022; also see Eifert, 1987; McConnell-Ginet, 2020). According to Pentón Herrera and Bryan (2022), the first formulations of the term ‘language weaponization’ date back to the 20th century when it appeared in (a) political sciences and (b) military studies—which took it to mean how languages are manipulated and controlled. Committee on Un-American Activities and S. T. Possony (1959) took language weaponization to mean how communists used to manipulate language to propagate and spread their ideology and doctrine, which they hoped would dominate the whole world (cf. Pentón Herrera & Bryan, 2022). Similarly, Kelling (1975) took language weaponization to mean how speech, discourse, media, etc. (i.e., the totality of language use) might be engaged in controlling people’s thoughts and behaviors (see also Dwight, 1980). In the 21st century, too, language weaponization has been a theme in diverse fields of inquiry, including linguistics, social sciences, and military studies; Pentón Herrera and Bryan (2022) list several important scholars that have addressed language weaponization in the 21st century, including Dovchin (2020), Fairclough (2015), Lupion (2018), McConnell-Ginet (2020), Pascale (2019), Rafael (2012), and Stahl (2016).

In their conception of the weaponization of language, Pentón Herrera and Bryan (2022) and Bryan and Pentón Herrera (2024b) have expanded the term to include the weaponization of ‘language education’, specifically educational (a) practices, (b) policies, (c) programs, and (d) curricula (see also Bryan & Gerald, 2020; Pascale, 2019; Rafael, 2016). As such, the weaponization of language has been brought to bear on issues of injustice in educational settings in addition to its traditional purviews that included social and political planes. In other words, this new conception of language weaponization addresses the processes via which harm, inequity and injustice are normalized and justified for minoritized individuals and their languages and cultures (cf. Baumgarten & Du Bois, 2019). This perspective on language weaponization presupposes the

existence of an intricate interface between language, discourse, and societal change (Bryan & Pentón Herrera, 2024a). It assumes that the way people use language in the process of communication has the 'affordance', à la Salman Nodoushan (2021b), to (a) shape perceptions, (b) foster dialogues, (c) impact social interactions, and (d) perpetuate harm against marginalized individuals and groups (Bryan & Pentón Herrera, 2024a).

In this connection, Rafi (2024) argued that the weaponization of the English language is a common practice in Bangladeshi English departments where Anglo-normative practices are promoted and the linguistic, cultural, and ideological dimensions of weaponization are regularly practiced. Likewise, Wu et al. (2024) have argued that (a) language weaponization—specifically, neoliberalist discourse—is part and parcel of ideological warfare in Taiwan's bilingual education policy, and that (b) it has been wielded in the rollout of Taiwan's Bilingual 2030 Policy to mobilize and garner public support for neoliberal educational reform. One important point in Wu et al.'s (2024) concluding remarks that supports the discussion presented in the following sections is that teachers and students have 'agency' and 'creativity', which they can bring to bear on language as well as its use in complex and dynamic global contexts.

Along the same lines, Bryan et al. (2024) argue that (a) racism, (b) colonization, and (c) standard language ideologies have indeed had dire impacts on the personal, social, and professional lives of African diasporas—i.e., Black peoples speaking local/minority languages that have paid insurmountable mental, economic, and sociocultural prices. Likewise, Chebanne and Monaka (2024) argue how (a) the use of English as the 'language of record' in all services of the state, and (b) the use of Setswana and English as the official 'languages of teaching' in schools have impacted the lives of more than twenty-five ethnic communities speaking various indigenous languages in Botswana; the consequences of this English-and-Setswana policy have resulted in the marginalization of local indigenous languages and their speakers who had to get assimilated into the larger society, a situation that has led to acute ethnic as well as language endangerment.

Similarly, Kemp (2024) has argued that language has been weaponized in the USA to uphold harmful practices and ideologies that (a) consider students and their Spanish deficient and broken, and (b) ignore the affordances that Spanish-speaking Latinx students bring to the classroom, including their rich linguistic practices and cultural knowledge. Kemp further argues that (a) language weaponization must be removed from classrooms, (b) forty years of marginalizing policies should come to an end, and (c) critical ideologies and practices should be introduced into the educational setting in the USA. Along the same lines, Descourtis (2024) argues that promoting standardized French

and marginalizing non-standard and slang forms of the language in the curriculum of US university-level French programs is essentially the weaponization of the curriculum that stigmatizes French slang users, thereby precluding students from learning a vital component of the French language and culture.

In a similar vein, Ríos Vega (2024) draws on lived experiences and personal anecdotes from US public schools to argue how oppressive language used in non-educational social settings gets automatically transferred into public schools. School administrative staff and ill-prepared pre-service and in-service teachers unknowingly use it to harm students of color in general and English language learners (ELLs) in specific. Rather than seeing their students as cultural and linguistic assets, they consider them as ‘objects’ for (purposes of) discrimination, stigmatization, and oppression. Ríos Vega argues that educators, teachers and school administrators should learn to aspire after an ethic of love instead of weaponizing language for oppression.

The studies reviewed above are only a handful of projects that represent a wide range of studies conducted on language weaponization. Nevertheless, different scholars have ‘weaponized’ different newly-coined, seemingly-professional terms to turn (the English) language on itself. Examples include ‘accentism’ (Dryden & Dovchin, 2022), ‘language incompetence’ (Canagarajah, 2022), ‘linguicism’ (Uekusa, 2019), ‘linguistic citizenship’ (Williams et al., 2022), ‘linguistic micro-aggressions’ (Piller, 2016), ‘translingual discrimination’ (Dovchin, 2022), ‘unequal Englishes’ (Tupas, 2015), etc. All of these ‘newly-weaponized’ terms illustrate (a) how language can be used outside of its ‘central function’ (i.e., its core affordance) of communication, and (b) how it can be engaged in ‘peripheral affordance’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021b) that change it into a ‘tool’ for inflicting what I would like to call ‘ideological othering’ on ‘others’.

3. Language weaponization or the weaponization of language?

No matter what you name it, language—in addition to its ‘deontological’ innate ‘affordance’ of communication—can also be wielded for other ‘teleological’ subsidiary purposes, including stigmatization, discrimination, oppression, persuasion, aggression, vilification, and so on. Nevertheless, I do not see much ‘truth’ in studies that ‘condemn’ language itself—specifically English—as being responsible for social problems in the emergence of which it has never had any ‘agency’. To be put to these ‘subsidiary’ functions, language needs a ‘living agent’, a human being if you will, who uses it to achieve their ideological intentions.

All in all, the question that has remained unanswered by sociolinguists who have addressed what they have collectively called ‘language weaponization’

(by which they, more often than not, mean ‘English/Spanish weaponization’) is whether vilification, stigmatization, oppression, aggression, conflict, discrimination, etc. are ‘innate’ and ‘deontological’ functions’ of language—i.e., the very specific purpose for which language was invented in the first place? Are they not the ‘teleological’ subsidiary uses to which language can be put by ‘willful human agents’ in much the same way as a surgeon can use a surgical razor blade to kill someone instead of saving their life? Is the ‘surgical razor blade’ to blame in the former scenario? If not, why ‘language’ should be?

In an earlier paper on ‘test functions’ versus ‘test affordances’, I drew an intricate clear borderline between test ‘function’ (i.e., the specific and designated use of a test), and test ‘affordances’ (i.e., other purposes for which the construct-irrelevant affordances of a test can be engaged)—cf. Salmani Nodoushan (2021b). I strongly believe that that distinction can be brought to also bear on sociolinguistic discussions of language weaponization. I also strongly believe that the ‘ethical use’ of a language (i.e., its innate function) has to be distinguished from the range of ‘unethical’ and ‘invalid’ uses (i.e., peripheral affordances) to which it can be put.

Affordances are the totality of the central functions and other subsidiary purposes into which any thingamabob can be put. Affordances can be classified as perceptible, false, or hidden (à la Gaver, 1991), or physical, cognitive, pattern, sensory, functional/explicit, and negative (à la Hartson, 2001). Take a chair as an example. It has been designed so that we can sit on it at a table, in a bar, etc. That is the ‘function’—i.e., the very specific purpose—it has been specifically designed to serve. The very fact that you can sit on a chair (i.e., engage its perceptible affordance) makes it ‘valid’. If its construction is weak and it breaks once you sit on it, it is still valid, but not reliable; its specific central function should never be mistaken for its ‘trustworthiness’. Nevertheless, we oftentimes put a chair under our feet, stand on it, and reach a top shelf. That is another ‘affordance’—or a peripheral affordance, if you will—of the chair, but not its core function or design(ated) affordance. The chair, besides its specific function, can ‘afford’ a good number of ‘construct-irrelevant’ purposes for the fulfillment of which it has not been designed in the first place—e.g., can be thrown out of the window, can be broken onto someone’s head in a pub fight among the drunk, and so forth.

(Salmani Nodoushan, 2021b, pp. 129-130)

For any sociolinguist to be fair and just, language cannot and should not ever be held responsible for what it has not been specifically ‘constructed’ to ‘function’ in “. . . in much the same way as chairs cannot and should not be denounced for being used in pub fights” (Salmani Nodoushan, 2021b, p. 130).

That said, the blame should only be put on those who use ‘the surgical razor blade’ of language outside of its ‘valid’ core function of ‘communication’ to ‘dehumanize’, ‘minoritize’, ‘other’, and ‘harm’ its non- or incompetent users and to question their (indigenous) languages, identities, ethnicities, and cultures.

It is by this token that I prefer ‘the weaponization of language’ over ‘language weaponization’. The latter seems to assign an ‘agentive quality’ to language. It seems to indicate that language is a self-detonating bomb that can explode itself in much the same way as a suicide-bomber does. The former term seems not to assign this ‘agentive quality’ to language. Notwithstanding the fact that all languages, including the indigenous ones, do possess ‘deontological slurs’ or ‘linguistic grenades’ pre-loaded with all forms of aggression (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016), no language can automatically ‘pull the pin out of them’ without the intervention of an external agent. It is always the human or institutional agent that detonates the loaded-weapon of language, but not the language itself. As such, no language can be held accountable for its being weaponized. All languages have this peripheral affordance, but they need the intervention of human/institutional agents to activate the affordance.

4. The status quo of Persian

Persian—also known as Farsi—is the ‘lingua franca’ spoken by almost all Iranian citizens and is the official language of government documents. It is a ‘pluricentric’ language (cf. Clyne, 1992), belonging to the Indo-Iranian subdivision of the Indo-European family, and its mutually intelligible standard varieties—i.e., Iranian, Dari, and Tajiki varieties—are spoken in Iran, Afghanistan, Tajikistan (and also in some other places including Uzbekistan, Turkey, Pakistan, etc.).

Throughout its history, Persian has gone through three phases: (1) Old Persian, which was the official language in the Achaemenid Empire (550-330 BCE); (2) Middle Persian, which was spoken in the Sassanid Empire (224-651 CE), and Modern Persian, spoken ever since the Samanid Empire era (819-999 CE) to the present day. Nevertheless, present-day Persian is not exactly the same as the Persian spoken during the Samanid Empire era, but has huge similarities to it. Old Persian, remnants of which are still extant in cuneiform inscriptions, is no longer intelligible to speakers of New Persian. Likewise, Middle Persian is not that intelligible either although it employed the first Aramaic-derived ‘alphabetic’ orthography in its inscriptions and in the writing of religious and official texts. The first records of New Persian (i.e., Farsi) literature date back to the ninth century (Abulghasemi, 1994).

Being the language of bureaucracy ever since the Samanid Empire era (819-999 CE), New/Modern Persian has played a great role in keeping the integrity of Iran and in uniting its different pedigree-Iranian ethnicities under one

national flag. Although Iran was invaded on several occasions by different foreign powers, including Arabs from Hijaz, Ottomans from Anatolia, Mughals from East Asia, and Pashtuns from non-Iranian parts of Afghanistan (cf. Egger, 2016), none of its invaders could impose their language on the Persians. Rather, they were so blown away by the grandeur and glory of Persia that they got integrated into the fabric of Persian society. With its rich literature, New Persian was so powerful and aesthetically mind-blowing that it impacted all other languages spoken in neighboring regions and beyond, including other Iranian indigenous languages, Arabic, Armenian, Georgian, the Turkic, and the Indo-Aryan languages.

In its lifetime, New Persian has undergone three phases: Early New Persian of the 8th to 9th centuries, (b) Classical Persian of the 10th to 18th centuries, and (c) Contemporary Persian of the 19th century to the present time. To be able to survive, New Persian opened itself to many foreign words, including words from Sogdian, Parthian, Mongolian, and Arabic languages (Frye, 1975)—see my discussion of Piaget's (1985) 'equilibrium', 'adaptation', 'assimilation, and 'accommodation' in Section 5 (below). New Persian started flourishing from the 11th century when it was adopted as the trans-regional 'lingua franca' by non-Iranian Central Asian Turks, Arabs, and other ethnic populations that lived in the region. Its relatively simple morphology and glorious literature made it possible for New Persian to win the hearts of all people who lived in the region and helped the language to grow until at least the 19th century (Johanson & Bulut, 2006). As a 'lingua franca' chosen by the people living in the region, it became the official and cultural language of many dynasties that cherished it. Up until the British colonization of India, New Persian was also the official language of the Sikh Empire (Johnson, 2001).

Ever since its emergence in the Samanid era until the early 20th century, New Persian never experienced government intervention and language planning. It has always been used as a 'lingua franca' by all pedigree-Iranian local ethnicities (i.e., Gilak, Mazandarani, Baloch, Azerbaijani, Turkmen, Qashqai, Assyrian, Armenian, Lur, Talysh, Tat, and so on); I call them 'pedigree-Iranian' to emphasize that they are pure-bred Iranian ethnicities in that they are the progenies of their Bronze Age Iranian ancestors; a comprehensive and exhaustive biological 'hybridization' took place on the surface of the Iranian Plateau after the migration of the Aryans (i.e., encompassing the Parthians, the Medes, the Scythians, the Sarmatians, etc.) into the Iranian Plateau about the Bronze Age (cf. Fisher et al., 1991). The intermarriage between the Aryans and the Persians (the original residents of the Iranian Plateau about the Bronze Age) resulted in the emergence of a 'hybridized' population that became the native population of Iran over time so that current-day Iranian ethnicities collectively come from that 'hybridized' common lineage; as such, these Iranian ethnicities can collectively be called 'pedigree' Iranians.

Present day Iranian ethnicities are 'biologically' and 'culturally' so integrated and interlaced with each other that it would not be wrong if we compared the fabric of the whole Iranian society to the 'warp' and 'weft' of a Persian carpet. In spite of their seemingly different local backgrounds, all of them consider themselves as pedigree Persians and are proud of the Persian language—albeit, with the exception of random politically-aspired foreign-supported whimsical and capricious individuals whose number is not that high to deserve any attention. The integration of the Iranian people is so mind-blowing that you will find 'in-laws' from other 'local ethnicities' (e.g., Fars, Baloch, Kurd, Gilak, Mazandarani, Azerbaijani, Turkmen, Qashqai, Assyrian, Armenian, Lur, Talysh, Tat, etc.) in almost all households and families all over Iran. Since the Samanid era (819-999 CE), all people who have lived in Iran have historically chosen New Persian for 'intercommunication'. Children in non-Fars families acquire it and become 'compound' bilinguals (cf. Liontas, 2018) for whom the two languages (New Persian and their indigenous dialects/languages) do not represent any situational distinctions.

During the Qajar dynasty (1789-1925), whose kings were mainly *Azeri-speaking Persians* (my emphasis), the Tehrani dialect of New Persian spoken in Tehran gained some temporary prominence—but this is no longer the case (see section 5 below). Language contact with Russian, French, and English resulted in huge lexical borrowings—I personally do not call them 'borrowings' or 'loanwords' since any language, including Persian, has countless 'accidental gaps'—or 'potential words'—that (a) are phonologically allowed by its phonology, (b) are part and parcel of its linguistic arsenal, (c) remain in its 'lexical attic', or 'morphology' if you will, for potential future use, and (d) have not been assigned any meaning yet. Cultural contact and industrial trade during this period resulted in the emergence of new words in Persian, especially those that relate to technology, art, and politics. Naser ed Din Shah of the Qajar dynasty opted for the standardization of Persian orthography in 1871, and the first Persian association was established in 1903 at the order of Mozaffar ed Din Shah of the Qajar dynasty. It was officially ordered that only the Persian and Arabic languages were acceptable sources for coining new words. Nevertheless, the main attempt at official language policy in the whole history of Iran that took place during the 1930s and 1940s—during the Pahlavi dynasty—did not target any Iranian indigenous dialects; being a 'foolish' and 'non-scientific' act, in my view, it only aimed at replacing the so-called foreign loanwords (e.g., Russian, French, Greek, etc.) with their Persian equivalents instead of accepting them as Persian 'lacunae' (i.e., 'accidental gaps', or potential 'dormant' words that currently do not exist at phonetic level, but do exist at phonemic level and are permitted by the rules of Persian);² it was a foolish language policy that is still going on, perhaps due

to 'treason' or 'lack of precise scientific understanding' of the workings of human language as a living organism.

Although it is true that it has been named as the only official language of bureaucracy, sovereignty, and government in the constitution of the country after the revolt of the late 1970s, Persian was by no means imposed on non-Fars dialectal/language groups. Rather, they willingly and unanimously voted for it in the constitutional referendum held in December 1979, in which over 99.5% of the population of the country voted 'Yes'. Moreover, the use of regional and tribal languages in press and mass media as well as their teaching and the teaching of their literature in schools are allowed. Article 15 in Chapter 2 of the *Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Iran*³ says:

The official language and script of Iran, the lingua franca of its people, is Persian. Official documents, correspondence, and texts, as well as textbooks, must be in this language and script. However, the use of regional and tribal languages in the press and mass media, as well as for teaching of their literature in schools, is allowed in addition to Persian.

Another important point that needs to be emphasized here is that the Azerbaijani and Arab groups that live in Iran are not of Arab or Turk descent; they are *not* 'pedigree' Arabs or 'pedigree' Turks (my emphasis). Their language has become Arabic or Azeri due to language contact at the borders of Iran. As such, applying the term 'ethnic' to them may not be valid if by ethnic one aims to mean 'pedigree' Arabs or 'pedigree' Turks. They are absolutely pedigree Iranians whose language has changed into Arabic or Azeri.

Nevertheless, certain political dissidents who were supported by the UK, Russia, and the Ottomans at the turn of the 20th century developed and propagated language and ethnic 'myths' that are void of even a grain of truth. In order to achieve their political goals of 'disintegrating' Iran and breaking it up into several small countries, random politically-aspired foreign-supported whimsical and capricious traitors (e.g., Khaz'al bin Jabir bin Merdaw al-Ka'bi in Khuzestan and Sayyed Ja'far Pischevari in Azerbaijan) did their best to fool the Arabic- and Azeri-speaking residents of those areas to accept that they are indeed 'pedigree' Arabs and 'pedigree' Turks; their attempts did not succeed, though. More recently, similar attempts are being made, and certain Kurdish, Turkish, Arab, and Baloch individuals are doing their best to disintegrate Iran.

5. Discussion

Notwithstanding the fact that 'language weaponization' has historically been 'utilized' by willful 'human' and 'institutional' agents to control, legitimize, delegitimize, stigmatize, colonize, and so forth, language itself cannot be

claimed to have ‘agency’ in and of itself. As stated at the end of Section 3 (above), this is not to deny the existence of ‘deontological slurs’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016) in the lexical arsenal of a language, but again, that ‘loaded weapon’, too, needs a willful ‘institutional’ or ‘human’ agent to pull the trigger. In other words, it is always the ‘human agent’ who wields language to the satisfaction of the personal, cultural, political, or social goals he or she craves to achieve.

By what went before, I do not intend to withstand the ‘given’ that many local languages of the world have been minoritized, and that their native speakers face challenges that have affected their lives. The remnants of colonization are still in place to motivate discrimination and spur globalization; faced with discrimination and forces of globalization, many indigenous people around the world have, unknowingly or otherwise, resorted to self-devaluating practices (cf. Pentón Herrera & Bryan, 2022) in aspiring after global participation and recognition. An entailment of this aspiration is that local languages will have to give in to a global lingua franca, a situation that is not that much unfamiliar to the people of Iran as they have already done so—see my discussion of the ‘warp’ and ‘weft’ of the Iranian society in the previous section.

In much the same way as New Persian has become the ‘lingua franca’ of a ‘culturally hybridized’, yet ‘integrated’, Iranian society, a universal lingua franca—e.g., English—is potentially able, and will be on the way, to become the integrating force that will unite a Huxleyan Brave New World. After all, in an earlier article published in *Rivista Italiana di Filosofia del Linguaggio*, Salmani Nodoushan (2021a), the current author, had the foresight to anticipate that the era of ‘open society’, à la Popper (1945), has finally arrived, and that children of the 21st century wield the English language as a ‘lingua franca’ to socialize in a ‘mediated’ way (on social media platforms), the result of which will be a universal ‘abstract society’ at the end of the day. According to Salmani Nodoushan (2021a, p. 215):

A third and new path for socialization has also emerged in the era of social media, a path that can be called socialization through social networks or simply ‘mediated socialization’. Some seventy-five years ago, Sir Karl Raimund Popper, the Austrian-British philosopher, expatiated upon the notions of open and closed societies first broached by Bergson (1932) to envisage the evolution of human societies as a continuum with organic communities at one end and abstract societies at the other (Popper 1945); now, it seems as if mediated socialization has already announced the debut and inauguration of abstract societies in the post-pandemic era.

In much the same way as pedigree-Iranian local ethnicities have historically used New Persian as a lingua franca to socialize into an integrated all-inclusive Iranian society, (non-)pedigree ethnicities and different nations from around the globe will use an all-encompassing lingua franca to socialize into a global abstract society; whether we like it or not, this burden has already fallen on the shoulders of the English language. Nevertheless, English itself has also been forced to pay a price. There are no longer only two standard varieties of English—spoken in the UK and the USA. New varieties have come about as a result of the process of ‘adaptation’.

I borrow the term ‘adaptation’ from Piaget’s famous theory of ‘adaptation’ in developmental psychology, which comprises two processes: assimilation and accommodation (Piaget, 1985). An organism—New Persian or English in our analogy—remains in a state of equilibrium with its surroundings (i.e., the ecosystem in which it lives) until something in the environment causes a state of disequilibrium. If the organism is intelligent enough, it can ‘adapt’ to this disequilibrium and reestablish the lost equilibrium; to this end, it has to go through the two processes of assimilation and accommodation. Through the former, it assimilates the new ecosystem by responding in ways that are consistent with its own existing schema; through the latter, it changes its own existing schema to create an entirely new schema which can accommodate the new ecosystem. In other words, the symbiotic intelligent organism first tries to assimilate or transform the changes in the ecosystem without changing its own needs or conceptions; where this is not possible, it will change itself and modify its own existing structures to accommodate the new changes in the ecosystem.

New Persian has been a hell of a resilient magician in doing so. It has craftily adapted itself to all invading forces over time (i.e., Arabic, Mongolian, Turkish, Russian, French, English, etc.) by accommodating incoming words in its morphology—albeit through the activation of its own accidental gaps—and simultaneously retaining its own syntactic and discursive integrity. After all, this is what a successful ‘lingua franca’ needs to do to survive. Specifically, this is exactly how New Persian has handled the invasion of Arabic. Perhaps this is also how standard varieties of English (i.e., American and British) have reacted to the new demands of the Huxleyan Brave New World; English has already paid the price of accommodating many non-standard varieties that are spoken in remote geographical areas of the globe as well as in the Popperian abstract society of social media. Being used as a lingua franca, English is going through the processes of change through which New Persian has already gone. I do see some difference between Persian and English, though. It seems, to me at least, that Persian has handled incoming attacks at only the morphological level—but this needs to be researched; perhaps the ‘in-situ’ nature of Persian relative clauses might prove me wrong. English, on the other hand, has apparently paid the price mainly at the syntactic level (in my view, at least). Examples may

include how temporal conjunctions, telic and atelic verbs, psychological predicates, possessives, etc. are used in non-standard non-native English-as-an-international-language varieties of English. This, of course, is just my vague premonition and needs to be researched before it can be scientifically accepted.

Perhaps indigenous languages in places where newly-emerged 'hybrid' varieties of English have become the 'language of communication' might not be happy. It was stated in section 2.1 (above) that, just like 'sexism', 'racism', etc., which inflict discrimination/segregation on groups of people based on sex, race, and so forth, 'linguicism' inflicts language-based discrimination. It was further stated above that, through linguicism, language is turned into a tool that can effectuate and maintain unequal access to, and allocation of, social and/or political power and material, economic, developmental, educational, and other forms of resources. However, it is not clear how and why people's use of varieties of English as the 'language of communication' should ever be called linguicism. On the one hand, if language is not used in the same way as sex, race, etc. are used to inflict inequality, it cannot be called linguicism. On the other hand, if language is used to inflict harm, it is the 'user' that should be reproached and held accountable, not the language; it is the user that has 'agency', not language. While I do understand the concerns of sociolinguists in formerly colonized countries (like India, South Africa, etc.), I do not have the same concerns about New Persian. It is true that some European colonists believed that the development of a unified integrated nation-state required the dismantling of indigenous societies and traditions. It is true that this belief has led to efforts to destroy indigenous peoples' languages and cultures (cf. Hamel, 2008). However, it is not true that this has happened in Iran. The Great Persian Empires of the past have never colonized any other country, nor did they urge their language or culture upon other countries.

As such, Persian colonization of the world is just a historical 'myth' and has never happened in reality; rather, the Great Persian Achaemenid Empire (550 BC-330BC) was the pioneer of human rights. It was an empire of 'leniency' and 'tolerance'. This claim is backed by the world's first 'charter of human rights', which was decreed by Cyrus the Great in 539 BC.

After he conquered the city of Babylon, Cyrus the Great (a) ordered that all slaves should be freed, (b) declared that all people had the right to choose their own religion, culture, and language, and (c) made sure to establish racial and gender equality. His orders were recorded on the famous 'Cyrus Cylinder' in the Akkadian language with cuneiform script (Finkel, 2013;

Figure 1.

The Cyrus Cylinder (539 BC)

Michalowski, 2007; Walker, 1972). Figure 1 displays the Cyrus Cylinder. Cyrus' charter of human rights has been the roadmap for all Iranians ever since its declaration in 539 BC, and Iranians have a long tradition of respecting and endearing non-Fars pedigree-Iranian local ethnicities, their regional dialects, and their local cultures. This has prevented them from weaponizing New Persian against indigenous Persian dialects as well as other languages that are spoken by non-Fars Iranians, especially Arabic, Kurdish, Balochi, and Azeri.

As stated above, Article 15 in Chapter 2 of the *Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Iran* has allowed the use and formal teaching of all non-Persian Iranian languages/dialects and their literature as well as their use in the press. It has also clearly stated that Persian is the official lingua franca that should be used as the language of bureaucracy. As such, claims about the weaponization of Persian against non-Fars pedigree-Iranian ethnicities are nonsense. Rather, some random politically-aspired foreign-supported traitors are weaponizing other indigenous Iranian languages/dialects against the nation's lingua franca. They insist that 'teaching *in* mother tongue' (my emphasis) should be allowed in addition to 'teaching the mother tongue', which has already been allowed in Article 15 of the nation's constitution. They militantly aspire after 'disallowing' the use of Persian—which is the mother tongue of all monolingual as well as polyglot citizens of Iran—as the language of instruction in schools located in areas with local non-Fars populations, whereby detaching them from their pedigree-Iranian identity and urging fake new identities upon them. It seems as if these militant culprits have clearly understood that 'teaching *in* mother tongue' (my emphasis) can open a window for them to inflict non-Fars ethnicities with 'identity' issues; they keep trying to go through this window with the final goal of disintegrating the unified country of Iran all of whose citizens speak Persian as a mother tongue and pedigree language in addition to their local dialects/languages.

As far as language teaching is concerned, one point in Wu et al.'s (2024) study reviewed above was that teachers and students have 'agency' and 'creativity', which they can bring to bear on language and its use in complex and dynamic global contexts. Based on this major premise, a minor premise has been proposed that claims if, for instance, a school ignored the mother tongues of kids who come from language minorities, it might have dire impacts on their learning (cf. Bryan & Pentón Herrera, 2024a; Chebanne & Monaka, 2024; Descourtis, 2024; Kemp, 2024; Rafi, 2024; Ríos Vega, 2024). A pseudo-syllogism—or an illicit fallacy, if you will—that emerges from these faulty major and minor premises is that 'teaching *in* a mother tongue/dialect' should be the one and only goal or mission of all schools and universities.

While I do not deny the importance of using students' local dialects/languages to scaffold teaching (which has been, and still is, done on a regular basis in

Iranian schools), I do not buy the above-mentioned illicit fallacy either. As stated before, all bilingual Iranians learn Persian as a ‘mother’ tongue along with their indigenous language/dialect and become compound bilinguals. As such, the use of Persian as the language of teaching and instruction is essentially the use of a *mother* tongue—i.e., the use of a *pedigree* language—as the language of teaching and instruction (my emphasis). As such, Persian is the mother/pedigree language for all Iranians, be they monolingual or polyglot; I myself come from Yazd, a province with Fars people, but we also have a local Yazdi dialect, which is not that intelligible to non-Yazdi Iranians, not even the Fars ones. The same is true about Semnan, Isfahan, Kerman, and all other apparently Fars provinces of Iran. It would not be wrong to claim that each city in Iran has its own local dialect, and that Persian does not belong to any specific city or province; Persian is simply what it is—a pedigree ‘lingua franca’, one that is glorious and has a rich graceful literature that unites all Iranians. As such, the use of Persian as the language for teaching and instruction does not cause issues of equity, identity, and comprehension for students.

In addition, the language of teaching and instruction is essentially a ‘language for specific purposes (LSP)’ (cf. Douglass, 2000; Salmani Nodoushan, 2020). The formal Persian that is used in schools and universities and on state media is not tantamount to any local Persian accent/dialect, not even the Tehrani dialect that received some temporary prominence during the Qajar dynasty (1789-1925), whose kings were mainly *Azeri-speaking Persians* (my emphasis). Formal Persian has naturally evolved over time to become a general non-local nation-wide ‘de-accented’ language that unites all Iranians from all local dialect groups. More specifically, it is a formal LSP used in formal or occupational settings—on state media, in schools and universities, in forensic settings, and so forth.

It was stated above (Section 2.1) that the impact of colonization on linguistic traditions depends on the form of colonization experienced: traders, settlers, or exploiters. In other words, whether colonization happens through trade, settlement, invasion, exploitation, or otherwise, its impacts will not be the same. Traders, for instance, did not impose their own European languages on the indigenous peoples of Africa; rather, they and their African interlocutors resorted to a new lingua franca (i.e., a pidgin language) that did not pose any threat to indigenous languages of Africa. In this connection, it must be said that the Persians—encompassing the Daens, the Ederousie, the Dropiques, the Elamtu, the Germanie, the Kassite, the Maraphies, the Mardes, the Maspes, the Panthialee, the Pasargadae, and the Sagarties (cf. Dandamaev & Lukonin, 2004; Frye, 1984; Herodotus, 2013)—were the original inhabitants of the Iranian Plateau before the arrival of the Aryans (encompassing the Parthians, the Medes, the Scythians, the Sarmatians, and all the other groups) who migrated into the Iranian Plateau around the Bronze Age. The Persians have never

colonized any parts of Iran; the Great Persian Empire has always been out there long before the emergence of New Persian around the Samanid era. Rather, this ancient empire has lost many of its parts due to foreign invasion by Arabs, Mughals, Russia, the UK, and so forth.

Although, historically speaking, the Persians have never colonized any parts of Iran, the Aryans (encompassing the Parthians, the Medes, the Scythians, the Sarmatians, and all the other groups) who migrated into the Iranian Plateau around the Bronze Age have gradually developed—in tandem with the Persians—a naturally-evolving language that their progenies and posterities have moved to a different level and are using as their uniting pedigree lingua franca. It would not be far from the truth if we claimed that New Persian is essentially the result of natural selection, à la Darwin (1859), not in the realm of flora and fauna, but in the linguistic realm.

6. Conclusion

Based on the information presented in the previous sections, it can be claimed that language weaponization should simultaneously (1) favor the dominant language over other languages in much the same way as racism favors a race over other races or sexism favors a sex/gender over another sex/gender, (2) be a structurally-manifested hegemonic ideology that allocates many more resources and infrastructures to the dominant language, (3) encourage claims that assign more prestige to the dominant language, (4) be a structural approach in that it envisages structural homology for language along with culture, education, media, and politics, (5) be essentially exploitative in order to cause injustice and inequality between those who do and do not use the dominant language, and (6) have a subtractive impact on other languages in that learning the dominant language should take place at the expense of the non-dominant (or recessive) ones.

All in all, New Persian does not possess any of the above qualities; no language does. Language weaponization is not a quality of any language; rather, it is a sinister quality of the individual or institutional agent that wields language to harm others. As ironically as it may seem, indigenous languages/and dialects are being weaponized by willful human agents against New Persian in Iran. To attain their goal of ‘disintegrating’ an ancient integrated country and breaking it up into several powerless new countries, random politically-aspired foreign-supported-and-commissioned whimsical and capricious traitor groups are weaponizing Arabic/Azeri/Kurdish/Balochi to mislead and fool pedigree-Iranian Arabic/Azeri/Kurdish/Balochi speakers to believe that they were and are separate ‘pedigree’ nations by virtue of their second mother tongues. These pathetic traitors have forgotten that, historically, the local populations of Iran have never been non-Iranian; the traitors have forgotten that the Arabic and

Azeri languages spoken at Iranian borders have been adopted by the pedigree-Iranian people living there, mainly due to language contact, need, and/or intercommunication with neighboring Arab and Turk nations. Likewise, the Kurds and the Baloch have always been pedigree Iranians. Collectively, we have always been one unified nation with one unifying pedigree lingua franca that has survived the winds of time along with our local dialects and languages. Together, we have cherished Persian and its glorious literature. Whether the random politically-aspired foreign-supported-and-commissioned whimsical and capricious traitors succeed or fail in their acts of treason is what only the test of time will tell.

Notes:

1. See Stavans' (2021) "The Spanish language in Latin America during the colonial period" about how the Spanish conquistadors coercively used language (Spanish) as a tool of colonization through spiritual, intellectual, and physical means. Also see La Belle and White's (1978) "Education and colonial language policies in Latin America and the Carriibbean."
2. For more on meaning in language, see Salmani Nodoushan (2022).
3. https://www.shora-gc.ir/files/en/news/2021/6/2/468_245.pdf

Acknowledgments

I am deeply indebted to Dr Chaka Chaka, Dr Hossein Heidari Tabrizi, and Dr Afsaneh Dehnad, who read an earlier draft of this paper and vetted it for precision and academic integrity.

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